

best beginnings
for every parent, for every child

LGBTQ+ MUMS RESEARCH

Identifying the needs and experiences of LGBTQ+ women in their journey to parenthood

October 2023

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Executive summary

Within the UK, changes in legislation over the past decade have altered the ways in which LGBTQ+ women can become parents. Evidence suggests that more openly LGBTQ+ people are having children each year, yet little is known about their needs or experiences.

Best Beginnings is a national charity established to help give every child in the UK the best start in life and reduce inequalities. We work collaboratively with parents, local communities, front-line professionals, service providers, professional bodies, academics and policymakers to create, disseminate and evaluate innovative interventions and drive positive change.

Best Beginnings in partnership with LGBT Mummies and the University of Huddersfield, commissioned this research to find out about the needs of LGBTQ+ women who had become parents in the last two years. Separate pieces of research are currently underway to investigate the needs and experiences of LGBTQ+ men in their journey to becoming a parent.

The findings from this research show that LGBTQ+ women had mixed experiences of services when trying to conceive, during pregnancy and birth, and in the early postnatal period. It suggests that changes to practice may not have kept pace with changes in legal and policy frameworks, but also highlights examples of excellent practice. Whilst most participants described their experiences of becoming parents as good overall, none had completely positive experiences, and the majority had some distressing experiences. Currently, LGBTQ+ women who are on the journey to parenthood face gaps in the information available to them in some areas and may face challenges to building a robust support network. There is significant room to improve the formal and informal perinatal support for LGBTQ+ women, and this report suggests ways that this work can be taken forward.

Authors

This report was compiled by Dr Mari Greenfield on behalf of Best Beginnings, in association with the University of Huddersfield and LGBT Mummies.

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Key points

A number of key areas were raised in the research, which are summarised below:

- Most participants enjoyed parenthood
- LGBTQ+ women who wish to conceive may face difficulties in obtaining accurate and appropriate information about conception options
- NHS perinatal services have historically been established for heterosexual couples, and may struggle to provide appropriate services for LGBTQ+ people
- Some LGBTQ+ women receive excellent care from some perinatal health services (this includes fertility clinics, midwives, obstetricians, health visitors and lactation support services). However, heterosexism remains pervasive in these services too
- Some healthcare professionals may have inaccurate information about Parental Responsibility for non-gestational mothers, leading in some cases to discriminatory treatment
- Non-gestational mothers lack access to appropriate perinatal mental health services
- Non-gestational parents who wish to breast or chestfeed their babies do not have adequate support. The lack of knowledge about co-feeding poses a risk for newborn babies
- Postnatal sexual health advice currently offered by the NHS may not be appropriate for LGBTQ+ women
- Using inclusive language is important for all perinatal service providers. The language currently used to describe LGBTQ+ parents is not static, and there is no agreed terminology, requiring a nuanced approach of everyone involved in providing perinatal services to that center's around individual parents' preferences
- A lack of family support, combined with changes to friendship networks and difficulties in accessing parenting groups may leave some LGBTQ+ parents isolated
- The uptake of Shared Parental Leave amongst LGBTQ+ women may be high
- Most participants experienced difficulties in registering their baby's birth. Additional training is required for Registrars
- Intersections of ethnicity, disability and class affect LGBTQ+ women's experiences of becoming parents

Introduction

Over the last few decades, the law has changed significantly for LGBTQ+ people in the UK who wish to become parents. Since 2009, two women have been able to be on a baby's birth certificate and the number of new two-mum families is increasing every year¹. So far, little is known about their experiences of pregnancy, birth and the first year of parenting.

Best Beginnings is a charity which aims to support every parent, and every child. Best Beginnings are the creators of the free, advert free, multi-award-winning, interactive pregnancy and parenting app Baby Buddy. The app provides evidence-based information and self-care tools, based on the latest research, across the perinatal journey. The Baby Buddy app supports frontline practitioners' work and communication. To understand how the app can better support LGBTQ+ women who are on the path to parenthood, it is crucial to understand the experiences of LGBTQ+ women who had had a child in the UK. Working in partnership with LGBT Mummies and the University of Huddersfield, Best Beginnings commissioned research into LGBTQ+ women's experiences of pregnancy, birth and early parenting, whether they were the gestational or non-gestational parent.

How the research was carried out

LGBTQ+ women over 18 who had either conceived a baby whilst in a relationship with another woman or conceived a baby as a solo parent were interviewed. To take part, their youngest child had to be under 2 years old, they had to live in the UK, and at least one of their children had to have been born in the UK. They could choose whether to take part in the interview alone or with partners.

16 participants were interviewed, all of whom had either one or two children. Seven interviewees had been gestational parents only, seven had been non-gestational parents only, and two were both gestational and non-gestational parents of their children. In terms of sexual orientation, seven identified as bisexual or pansexual, eight as lesbian, and one was unsure. Four of the participants said they were disabled, and listed a variety of disabilities including cerebral palsy, epilepsy, autism and mental health conditions. There were also two neurodivergent people who do not identify as disabled, and 10 non-disabled interviewees. Interviewees were from a range of ethnic backgrounds, shown below:

The interviews were transcribed and analysed by the researcher, using Thematic Analysis methodology^{2,3}. After the interviews, participants were asked to create an account on the Baby Buddy app, using a fictional character created for them. They were then asked to rate aspects of the app, including information, videos, and an article.

In addition, three healthcare professionals who had provided perinatal care to LGBTQ+ women were interviewed. They were asked about their training, good and bad practices and policies that they had seen, and what made it easier for them to provide good care to LGBTQ+ women. The healthcare professionals included one obstetric registrar and two NHS midwives, all currently in practice, all of whom were LGBTQ+. To preserve anonymity, no further demographic details of the healthcare professionals are provided and gender-neutral pronouns are used for them throughout.

LGBTQ+ women's experiences of becoming parents

The majority of the experiences described by the LGBTQ+ women in this research were similar to the experiences of heterosexual people who become parents. All the participants enjoyed being parents

'It's awesome. It's one thing I'll never regret!'

(Lina)

although many struggled with similar issues to their heterosexual peers, such as changes to their bodies, relationships, lives, and especially the amount of sleep they got. Others also faced more serious challenges to their mental health and wellbeing, as do some heterosexual parents. There were also areas where some or all of the participants had experienced that were different to their heterosexual peers, which are reported below.

Getting pregnant

Most LGBTQ+ women who are trying to conceive whilst in a relationship with another woman will experience 'social infertility'⁴. Participants in this research had conceived in a variety of different ways. Some had conceived at home, using artificial insemination with a known donor. Others had conceived in a fertility clinic, some via intrauterine insemination (IUI) and some via in vitro fertilisation (IVF), whilst two women had conceived at home through intercourse with their partners who were trans women. Regardless of the method of conception, most participants had found it difficult to get accurate information from

Social infertility means they cannot conceive/carry a baby because they don't have access to the needed gametes (sperm and eggs)

healthcare professionals about conception.

Preconception information

The conditions required to access NHS fertility treatment mean that almost no women who are not in a sexual relationship with a man can access free treatment. Although the new Women's Health Strategy appeared to resolve this when it was launched in August 2022, it has recently been clarified that creating equitable access to fertility treatment is the Department of Health's ambition for their 10-year plan, rather than an immediate change introduced by the Strategy. Despite this lack of access to fertility treatments, everyone is entitled to access certain tests, and to be referred to a fertility clinic by their GP. Many women will visit their GP as a first step in finding out about conception options^{5,6}. In this research, one couple approached their GP to find information about their options for treatment. Their GP told them that she didn't have any information about that, and then after the appointment made a referral to a private fertility clinic without their permission.

Another participant described inappropriate advice given by their GP:

'The GP told my wife – while I was sitting there – to go and sleep with a man and see if that would get anything going'

(Buffy)

Not only was this advice distressing to both women, but had they followed this advice, the non-gestational mum would not have been the legal parent to her baby.

Another wanted to be referred to a specific fertility clinic, as it was the only one in the UK at that time that had sperm from a Black donor available. Although she would need to pay for treatment, she needed a referral from the GP to be treated by the clinic. She had multiple appointments with different GPs, as several refused to make the referral. Each time she provided more evidence from NHS information to prove she was entitled to be referred.

I had four GP appointments. The first two didn't know what IUI was. All of them thought that on the NHS you weren't entitled to any initial blood work in relation to fertility'

(Fatima)

Poor access to accurate medical information was also a difficulty for trans women. The current NHS advice is that a trans women who wishes to have children in the future should preserve her gametes prior to hormonal therapy^{7,8}. If hormonal therapy has already begun, she is required to cease treatment for 6 months before storing her gametes, due to an expectation that her sperm number and quality will be low⁸. Simple low-cost fertility tests are available to check this, but they are not carried out prior to the cessation of hormonal therapy. Pausing hormonal therapy can cause significant distress for transgender people⁸.

'The six months to bank sperm, that was NOT a good time at all'

(Margot)

Many trans women later impregnate their partners without ceasing hormonal therapies,

challenging the current NHS policy⁹⁻¹², which was the case for this couple. This can leave transgender people and their partners with significant information gaps about either attempting to conceive or avoiding pregnancy.

Almost nobody knows anything about trans fertility'

(Lilja)

Conceiving at home

For LGBTQ+ people who have the capacity to become pregnant, but lack access to sperm within a romantic relationship, making the decision about whether to conceive at home or via a clinic is the first step towards parenthood.

About half of the participants chose to conceive at home. Reasons for this included:

- wanting children to be able to form a relationship with their donor
- facing racism from fertility clinics
- a lack of suitable sperm donors
- being over the BMI cut-off for clinical treatment
- prohibitive costs of clinics
- a wish to avoid a highly medicalised conception.

Some participants considering conceiving at home with someone they had met through a donor website, but none pursued this option. Those who had investigated this option commented that there were a mixture of genuine donors, some of whom had donated to a high number of families, and men looking for sex on the sites.

Conceiving with a known donor at home was described by those who had chosen this route as having potential benefits for the child, but also as carrying significant risks should the donor decide he wanted either lesser or greater involvement in the future. Some participants who had chosen either path to conception continued to question whether they had made the right decision even after their baby was born.

'If we'd been able to find a known donor who we trusted and respected, that would have definitely alleviated some of the loss for me, but it would've also added another really, really big layer of anxiety and complexity in terms of parental rights and things that I think donors can't anticipate'

(Meira)

Several participants who had attempted to conceive at home described the difficulty of asking friends if they would help them make a family. Most had found it to be an embarrassing and risky conversation, for which there was not a social script. In some cases, asking friends if they would consider being a donor had ended a friendship, reducing the social support that was available to the participants as they embarked on their journey to parenthood.

'It's the weirdest conversation to have. How does one go about asking your friend for his sperm?'

(Hannah)

Those who had conceived with a known donor described various processes they had used to try to ensure that the donor was a good match for their family. This included lengthy exchanges over several months ensuring that their expectations and values matched, as well as health checks and fertility checks for some participants.

Fertility clinics

Participants who chose to use a fertility clinic rather than conceive at home did so for a variety of reasons, including:

- lack of a suitable donor within their social circle
- the ability to register their partner as a parent without getting married or civilly partnered
- vetting of the donor's health
- avoidance of future changes in the donor's wish for involvement.

Some participants had considered importing sperm from countries where non-anonymous donors are available, whilst others had ethical concerns about importing sperm, especially from the USA.

Those who had used a fertility clinic commented on the cost, and the financial pressures this had placed them under before they entered parenthood. Whilst one person had conceived using IUI, those who had used IVF estimate that having a baby had cost them around £30,000 – £40,000. One couple had had three IUIs, before moving to IVF. However, during their first IVF attempt, the clinicians needed to use intracytoplasmic sperm injection (ICSI), because of the low motility of the sperm, which came from the same donor. This made the participant question whether they should have been refunded for the IVF treatment, but they found they had no recourse.

All of the participants who had had IVF were aware that changes to the requirements for women in same-sex relationships to undergo 12 months of IUI before qualifying for IVF via the NHS were likely in the years ahead. However, if a person is listed on birth certificate, they and their partner are ineligible to receive IVF via the NHS, regardless of their gender or sexual orientation. Participants expressed frustration that because they had one child to whom they were both the legal parent, both parents would now be ineligible to receive free treatment, even though they had paid so much to conceive their first child. Even Fatima – whose wife was the non-gestational parent to her previous partner's child – would not be eligible to receive treatment, despite the fact that neither Fatima or Aisha had given birth.

Participants found the experience of choosing a donor conceptually challenging. The donor's ethnicity was the most commonly mentioned important factor, with health, physical characteristics that resembled the non-gestational parent and donor motivation also being mentioned.

At a national level, there are proportionately lower numbers of Black and Asian sperm donors. This made choosing donors difficult for some participants, especially if the non-gestational parent was Black or Brown and the gestational parent was white.

Most participants who had talked to a fertility clinic about assisted conception felt they were strongly encouraged towards IVF. The only participant who had not experienced this pressure was also the only participant to have conceived through IUI, and she stated that the clinic she attended did not offer IVF.

'We couldn't find any Black or mixed race sperm donors. I'm mixed race. So we had to choose, a white donor in the end, which was very difficult for us to make that decision'

(Florence)

Several participants were told that IVF has a higher success rate than IUI, but felt that this was not evidence-based, as the statistics are based on all fertility clinic patients, who are mostly heterosexual couples with medical fertility difficulties, rather than women who have social infertility.

'Who are these statistics representing? I don't think they segmented out same sex couples from people who are struggling to conceive'

(Pallas)

Several Black participants found their experiences with fertility clinics uncomfortable. There are low numbers of Black egg donors in the UK, and some Black participants felt they were immediately encouraged by clinics to have IVF, and to reduce the cost of this by 'egg-sharing' – that is donating some of their eggs to other patients in return for reduced treatment costs. One couple said

*'They were just seeing us as like little pots of money...
We're here to start our own family, not for you to harvest our eggs because we're Black and start somebody else's family'*

(Marcia and Cleo)

Some forms of assisted conception come with higher risks of complications¹³, including stillbirth and perinatal death¹⁴, but there is no evidence that conceiving through IUI at a clinic or artificial insemination at home carries these increased risks. Current NHS and NICE guidance says that all assisted conceptions should be classed as high-risk pregnancies, and does not differentiate between IVF with donor eggs, IVF, IUI in a clinic or artificial insemination at home¹⁵⁻¹⁷. All the participants who had conceived at a clinic had been told that assisted conception increased the chances of complications

The midwives and obstetrician who were interviewed expressed frustration at having to make or receive obstetric referrals based on the guidance that assisted conception meant a high risk pregnancy when women had conceived through IUI or at home through artificial insemination. Some chose not to make referrals for women who had conceived at home, and some described how obstetricians in their NHS Trust would immediately discharge people in this situation with no additional risk-factors back to midwifery-led care, which they felt was good practice.

and stillbirths, but none had been told that this only applied to IVF, not to IUI or home inseminations.

However, the majority of the LGBTQ+ women in this research received care in NHS Trusts that follow the current advice to treat all assisted conceptions as high-risk pregnancies. This means that the advice they received about the risks and benefits of induction of labour or caesarean births was likely to be inaccurate.

Family formations

LGBTQ+ families can take many different forms, and there is evidence that diverse relationship and structures are more common amongst LGBTQ+ people than amongst their cisgender heterosexual peers^{18,19}. Diversity in relationship structure and gender require those working with LGBTQ+ families to adapt their language and practice to each family, rather than to simply substitute one set of gendered terms within a standard mono-normative nuclear family model for a different set of gendered terms.

Whilst the majority of participants in this research were cisgender women were in monogamous relationships, raising children that they had planned together, some were also not. Gender diversity included lesbian couples where one woman was cisgender and the other was transgender, who had conceived together through intercourse. Some of the participants also considered themselves to be both women and non-binary, whilst others had non-binary partners.

'Aisha is comfortable being referred to as my wife, but identifies as nonbinary. For pronouns she is happy and comfortable with she/her and they/them'
(Fatima)

One participant was in a polyamorous relationship and had multiple partners. Other families had a known sperm donor who was present in their life. This is a role that is largely undefined by society – participants were clear that this person was not a parent, nor part of the central family unit, but that they did hold a different role to other friends. Some participants were also in contact with the donor's family – a relationship that there are no terms for.

Some participants were also raising children from previous relationships. In some cases these children were not genetically related to the participant or to their partner:

'Tupi is my step baby, Aisha's daughter from her previous marriage, which also to a woman, Tupi's gestational mother'
(Fatima)

Diversity also existed in participants' families of origin. Some participants were adopted, or had been fostered. Several participants were not in contact with their parents or siblings, whilst others were very close. Some had a closer relationship with in-laws. Others had

'chosen families' – a common family form for LGBTQ+ people who have been rejected by their family of origin – who continued to provide familial support as participants became parents

Making decisions

Participants described making decisions about who should become pregnant, how to conceive, and which donor to choose as a couple. Many of these decisions began at an early point in the relationship; in one case this was the first conversation between the couple on their first date. Other participants described ending previous relationships over disagreements not about whether to have children, but about parenting decisions they wished to make about future children. These decisions were described as collaborative, involving all partners on a reasonably equal basis.

'Our polycule had a meeting at a pub for choosing names, then basically we all went away and started researching gender neutral names and putting them in a spreadsheet'

(Chloe)

For most participants there was a significant amount of time between making the decision to have children and actually conceiving. This was a result of social infertility, and was especially lengthy where participants needed to save money for expensive assisted conception treatments. Several participants commented that one effect of this was that they had talked extensively about parenting decisions prior to conception.

Decisions once conception had happened were described differently. Several non-gestational parents described their role as researching options about medical tests and birthplace or birth choices. There was a strong sense that decisions during pregnancy and in the immediate postnatal period should be made by the person who was pregnant, as they involved her body.

'These were all led by my partner because she was the pregnant one'

(Pallas)

After the immediate postnatal period, decisions were once again described as being a joint responsibility, shared between the partners on an equitable basis.

'I took the lead on the cloth diapers. I did a lot of research and picked out the different diapers and ordered them. And Lilja was just like, there's diapers, I like them'

(Margot)

Support

Having supportive care from healthcare professionals is shown to improve birth outcomes for all parents and babies, including reducing stillbirth²⁰ and pre-term birth rates²¹, and protecting against birth trauma^{22,23} and some associated perinatal mental health conditions such as PTSD^{24,25}. Similarly, having a supportive social network has been proved to reduce the incidence and severity of perinatal mental health conditions such as postnatal depression and anxiety for all parents^{26,27}. LGBTQ+ parents may face greater challenges than cisgender heterosexual people in securing support as they become parents due to heterosexism, homophobia and transphobia²⁸.

Healthcare professionals

Most participants said that the majority of the care they had received from healthcare professionals during the perinatal period was good. The majority had some extremely positive experiences, and expressed gratitude for the skilled and compassionate care they received. However, all but one participant also described receiving poor care (e.g., incorrect co-breastfeeding advice, heterosexist or homophobic comments) on at least one occasion during the pregnancy, birth or early postnatal period. The inability to predict when care would be good and when it would not be stressful.

Many participants described small incidences of heterosexism, where a healthcare professional assumed that they were heterosexual because they had a baby. Participants did not describe these incidents as poor care but found them irritating and annoying. These incidents also made them wary, concerned that poor care might follow.

The nurse was asking the baby, 'Is daddy not here today?'

(Helen)

Heterosexist assumptions may also result in assumptions about the relationship between two people based on their gender. A difficulty experienced by a number of participants was that people working in clinics and hospitals assumed that if two women came for an appointment, they were sisters or friends. Often this assumption was not made by healthcare professionals, but by reception staff.

'At the hospital, she said 'You're not allowed to bring your friends with you, it's partners only'. And I said 'she's my wife'. And she didn't get it quite at first. And then she had to go and check, and she took ages to check it.'

(Marcia)

Other non-gestational parents faced similar situations, and were told they were not permitted into appointments and scans due to the pandemic restrictions, which they did not challenge as they assumed it meant all gestational parents had to go into the room alone. However, when they noticed other pregnant women being accompanied by men into the appointments

and scans, they realised that their relationship had been mistakenly interpreted. Whilst not universal, barriers to being allowed to physically be with their partner were a common experience reported by all participants for antenatal appointments, and reported by non-gestational parents when they visited their partner and new baby postnatally.

'I mean you should be able to like get into a hospital without the receptionist giving you grief'

(Chloe)

Appropriate ways to overcome these heterosexist assumptions – and the denial of access that followed them – was a difficulty discussed by the healthcare professionals who were interviewed. One healthcare professional participant described how, in the absence of anywhere appropriate to record this information, it was standard practice in one obstetric ward to write 'lesbian' in the risk section of the patient information board. Whilst this was only visible to staff, they felt it was inappropriate to reveal the sexual orientation of some patients and not others, potentially inaccurate as some same-sex couples would include bisexual women, and risked conflating lesbian parenthood with safeguarding issues.

Another healthcare professional described the practice in their clinic of verbally communicating that a family was a same-sex couple during the shift handover to another midwife. They felt this was good practice, but noted that there was a difference in how information was communicated when a couple were heterosexual. For heterosexual couples, the new midwife would be told the gestational parent's name, that their partner, mother, friend, doula or other birth supporter was with them, and what their name was. However, when a midwife handed over a same-sex couple, they would usually say that they were caring for 'a lovely lesbian couple', and then give both names. The participant speculated about reasons behind this difference, which they felt certain arose from a positive motivation. Nonetheless, the difference continued to make them feel uncomfortable.

Antenatally, some participants reported that they were treated differently by healthcare professionals once they disclosed that they had conceived at home with a known donor, rather than via a clinic.

'It felt like they were digging quite a lot into the donor. And I'm like, there's women that come in here that don't know that even know who the father is. So how is this such a big thing?'

(Cleo)

'He said I would have to have IVF. I said we're planning to inseminate at home. He said, 'Oh, so you're going to have intercourse with the donor?' And I'm like, how are you a fertility specialist doctor?'

(Hannah)

They described feeling a sense of disapproval from healthcare professionals that they had not conceived via a fertility clinic, and found they were asked lots of questions about whether their donor had been screened for sexually transmitted infections. Those who had heterosexual friends who were at a similar stage of pregnancy noticed that their friends were not asked about whether their male partners had been screened for sexually transmitted infections. Others found that healthcare professionals were not as well informed about LGBTQ+ conception as they would have liked.

Several non-binary and transgender participants said that healthcare professionals often got their pronouns wrong, or displayed discomfort with the fact the participant or their partner was not cisgender. For one participant, this went further, and involved an interview with a healthcare professional that the participant found distressing:

'They were treating it [being trans] as if it was like a safeguarding issue. One of my biggest concerns about being a queer parent in a polycule is a malicious referral to social services'

(Isabelle)

Postnatally, a high number of participants reported invalidation of their parenting relationships from healthcare professionals. This ranged from questions about who gave birth in situations where this information was unnecessary, such as during infant vaccinations:

'After the baby was born we had a lot of, 'Okay, but which one of you is the real mum?''

(Hannah)

In more extreme cases, some participants experienced some healthcare professionals refusing to communicate at all with non-gestational parents because they did not realise they were the baby's legal parent.

'She absolutely refused to speak to me. We've got a two seater sofa and a chair and I was sat on the sofa. She was sat in the chair and to speak to Spike, she would crane her neck round to speak past me, absolutely refusing to speak to me. She kept insisting that I needed a parental order agreement for me to have any say in Willow's care or anything. But I'm on the birth certificate!'

(Buffy)

The nurses were fairly horrendous. There was a couple of times when it was 'Who's mummy?' Well, we're both mummy'

(Meira)

Although the healthcare professional later did agree to speak to Buffy, saying that she had been unaware of the legal changes to birth registration in 2009, Buffy and Spike did not wish to see this healthcare professional again. As their baby had some health difficulties, this

resulted in them having to travel to a neighbouring town to access healthcare.

Healthcare professionals' confusion about non-gestational parents resulted in a situation where, after a participant said during a new baby check that both of the women present were the baby's mother, the participant was told

'You know, mum's friend, you could wait outside'

(Fatima)

However, the healthcare professional in this case had wrongly assumed that the non-gestational parent was the gestational parent, and so had in fact just asked the gestational parent to leave the room. This incident was particularly distressing to the participant and their partner as their four-year-old was also present, and they did not want her to witness this kind of discrimination and invalidation of their family.

Family relationships

Participants had very different experiences in terms of family support. Before conception, some participants' families had been very supportive of their desire to conceive, offering emotional and practical support and in some cases financial support.

'My aunties have chipped into the Demi pot. We call them the investors'
(Helen)

One participant described having an already strong relationship with her parents, and felt that having grandchildren had strengthened that relationship even further.

Other participants had been worried before or during pregnancy that the relationship with their family might be damaged by their decision to have a baby. Usually this was because of comments that family members had made sometime before.

'When we bought this house, I said to Spike, this'll be really nice for when we have kids. And my mum screamed across the street 'over my dead body'. So for the last 10 years before we got pregnant, that's what I thought my mum's attitude was'

(Buffy)

Worrying about family reactions had an impact during pregnancy. Buffy and Spike told their parents they were pregnant at 6 weeks gestation, to give them as long as possible to get used to the idea. Marcia and Cleo said that even though their families were lovely with the baby once he arrived:

'Our families don't agree with our relationship and use religion to justify their actions and thoughts. I didn't want to get pregnant and

miscarry and they'd say it was God's plan – 'He didn't want you to be pregnant because you two are in a same sex relationship'

(Marcia)

As a result, Marcia was extremely careful about ensuring her vitamin levels, weight and general health were exactly at the recommended points before conception. During pregnancy she monitored her own health and her baby's movements every day, having several private scans when she felt her baby's movements had been unusual. Marcia found it put a lot of pressure on her to be:

'Hypervigilant about everything'

(Marcia)

Once the baby was born, around half the participants found that having a baby had brought their family closer, sometimes healing rifts or distance that had arisen.

'It did really change our relationship with our in-laws. I had never met Margot's parents before and then they came over to meet Atlas'

(Lilja)

Positive changes seemed to be most common between participants and their parents, or their partner's parents, with fewer describing significant changes in their relationships with siblings, grandparents, or wider family. Participants who had experienced positive changes to their family tended to feel that it was natural for relationships between parents and children to improve when grandchildren were born.

'I think babies soften people don't they?'

(Cleo)

For some participants, the arrival of the baby was the moment at which their parents became more accepting of their partner, because their parents were keen to have a relationship with their grandchild.

'I think it forced my mum particularly into the process of accepting some things'

(Helen)

For other participants, although having a baby brought their family closer, difficulties existed in the language the wider family used to describe their relationship to their baby. Both cisgender non-gestational mothers and trans mothers said that some members of their family refused to refer to them as a mother. In one case where a participant had an older child, this included a grandparent telling the child that the non-gestational mother was not her mum when the child called her that, causing distress to both the mother and child. In some cases participants felt that the family's discomfort with language was due to a lack of knowledge or understanding about the appropriate terms to use and could be corrected with enough repetition, whilst in other cases participants were clear that the family's choice not to use

maternal terms was a deliberate choice, used to express their view that non-gestational mothers were not parents.

About half of the LGBTQ+ women interviewed found that having a baby did not bring their families closer. Sometimes this was because their families disapproved of same-sex relationships, and felt that having children made the relationship more official, or because they believed it was damaging to children to grow up in an LGBTQ+ family. In other cases, the non-gestational mother's family did not see the baby as part of their family, or see the non-gestational mother as the baby's parent.

'I feel like my family haven't been as supportive. Because he's not my biological child. I've been very disappointed'

(Pallas)

For a few participants, the decision to have a baby had made the relationship with their family worse.

'I've been disowned by my family'

(Fatima)

Some participants whose relationships with their parents or their partners' parents had become more distant after having a baby identified the emotional and practical cost this imposed on them. One referred to this as an LGBT parent tax.

'One of our mum friends, little one goes to grandparents and aunties. And I do feel, and I shouldn't, but I do feel very jealous of the fact that she goes out, or she'll have a good night's sleep once a week because she's not got a child at home. And we don't have that'

(Buffy)

Disconnection from family, whether this had happened some time before or as a result of deciding to have a baby, was experienced as very painful for every participant who experienced this. Black and Asian participants, who had sometimes become disconnected from not only family, but from their wider cultural community due to homophobia and transphobia, felt a specific responsibility to pass on their cultural heritage to their child.

'Because I'm disconnected from my family, I feel more pressure as an LGBTQ person, because there's no other source of the culture or the background for my children'

Friendships

Some participants felt extremely well supported by their friends as they became parents, and were grateful for the care they experienced.

'One of our friends came over and brought us food for our freezer and came to do dishes. Just, physical simple, I've showed up with food and I'm going to leave. It was amazing'

(Lilja)

Many people find that their friendship group changes as they become parents²⁹, and that is true for LGBTQ+ women who become parents too²⁸. This was also experienced by a number of the participants. For some participants, this had been a positive change, as new friendships with other parents were forged.

"We made a lot of really good friends through [parenting group] too. So now we've got quite a good network of parents in our area'

(Hannah)

In one case, a participant had used a known donor to conceive, who had been an existing friend. After her two children were born, that friendship had become more important in the participant's life. For other participants, becoming parents had resulted in a loss of long-standing friendships.

'Our main friends are no longer main friends since we've had Benjamin.'

(Cleo)

However, amongst cisgender heterosexual people, starting a family is seen as a usual life course event, and therefore some friendships are likely to continue or restart as other people in the social circle also have children²⁹. Although the number of openly LGBTQ+ people having children is increasing, it has not yet become a standard lifecourse event¹. Because of this, changes to friendship groups may be more common, or involve a change to the entire friendship network, amongst LGBTQ+ new parents²⁸. This is significant because having a strong social network is known to improve the wellbeing of new parents and babies²⁹.

Amongst the participants in this study, a range of reasons were given for changes to friendship networks. These included: having high numbers of friends who did not want children or who did not enjoy spending time with children; having LGBTQ+ friends who wanted children but could not afford the necessary fertility treatments to conceive, and who therefore found being around other LGBTQ+ people's children challenging. The disappearance of a whole social network left some participants feeling isolated.

'It is very much just the three of us until we find new friends'

(Cleo)

A commonality was that participants' social networks had changed to include solely or mostly cisgender heterosexual people. Whilst participants who had developed new friendships with other parents found these invaluable, many expressed that they would also value friendships with other LGBTQ+ parents.

'To be our authentic selves it would be nice to be able to meet other families like us'

(Cleo)

Making friends with other LGBTQ+ parents posed a challenge for the majority of the participants, as there are fewer LGBTQ+ parents. A number of participants said they had moved city prior to having their baby, to maximise the chances of finding LGBTQ+ parents to befriend. Sometime this was successful, especially where there was specific provision such as a local LGBTQ+ parents' group. For others, despite moving, finding LGBTQ+ parents who had children of a similar age and who participants shared interests with was almost impossible. The lack of peers was experienced as especially difficult by non-gestational mothers.

'It'd be great to be able to reach out to parents that aren't the biological parents just to see what their thoughts are'

(Cleo)

'I've been trying to look for someone who's in my position. It's hard to find non-birth mothers or same-sex couples'

(Pallas)

Partners

All the participants in the study had at least one partner. Having their partners' support during pregnancy, birth and the early postnatal period was described by the majority of the participants as essential. Due to the timing of this research, most participants had experienced Covid 19-related restrictions which meant their partners not being allowed to attend some appointments. This was an experience shared by heterosexual people who were pregnant at the same time, but it had consequences for LGBTQ+ parents that it did not have for heterosexual parents. Several participants said that, without their partner with them, they were assumed to be heterosexual during healthcare appointments. The sense that their identity was not seen, and that an important relationship in their life was made invisible caused distress and disconnection from healthcare professionals who were offering care.

'There was always the assumption that you are like one half of a heterosexual couple, especially since I was going to appointments alone because of covid, so we weren't 'out' automatically. And

sometimes I was feeling pregnant and vulnerable, I didn't feel like having that conversation with a nurse I'd never see again'

(Lilja)

To compensate for this, almost half of the participants used private services for some pregnancy care, including doulas, independent midwives, and private sonographers.

'We [had scans] privately before NHS ones, so there weren't any surprises. And if there were, we could be together'

(Meira)

Other research has suggested that LGBTQ+ parents in the UK may be more likely than cisgender heterosexual parents to use such services³⁰.

The need to have a partner present during anything connected to the pregnancy and birth was so strong for some participants that it influenced the care they chose:

'That was the reason why we chose the hospital. It was the only one that allowed her to stay over in the postnatal ward'

(Meira)

In this case, making the decision to give birth in the only hospital that allowed a partner to stay overnight in the postnatal ward involved travel of some hours to each antenatal appointment.

Choosing parental names is one way in which partners provided affirmation of parenting role to each other. For LGBTQ+ families, decisions about what the child should call each parent have fewer social scripts than for cisgender heterosexual parents. All participants described having conversations with partners about which names they wished to be called. Sometimes names were chosen based on the parents' cultural heritages, in some families both parents used 'mum'. For a high number of those where one parent was called 'mum' or 'mummy' and the other was called by a parenting name that is less common in the UK, the non-gestational mother was the one who was referred to as 'mum' or 'mummy', with the gestational parent taking the less common title. Several participants who were gestational parents said they had suggested this, and their motivation in making this choice was to reaffirm the connection between the non-gestational parent and the baby in the context of a society that would not always recognise this connection. Several also described a sense of loss and sadness at not being referred to as 'mum' or 'mummy' themselves, but felt that this sacrifice was appropriate to provide support to their partner. Similarly, in some couples the non-gestational parent was the one to choose the baby's name, and this was again described by participants as a sacrifice the gestational parent had made in order to bolster the validity of the non-gestational parent's relationship with the baby against a society in which this would not always be recognised.

Changes to relationship between partners after the birth of the first child are common amongst all parents^{31,32}. Commonly reported difficulties include a lack of time for each other, stress, and feeling unsupported by a partner^{33,34}. Every participant in this research said they felt

supported by their partner, and only one participant said that they felt their relationship had been negatively impacted. However, participants also acknowledged that they had less time for each other and had experienced more stress following the birth of their baby. Accessing appropriate relationship support seems likely to be as important for LGBTQ+ parents as it is for cis-gender heterosexual parents.

Some non-gestational parents had always planned to be, or had become, the primary carer for their child. They identified ways in which they forged a different connection with their child than the other parent(s), often through doing having certain groups or activities that only they did with their child.

'Tupi speaks a language that she shares only with me. She calls me Ammi, which is mum in Urdu'

(Fatima)

No participants who were non-gestational parents described feeling left out by the demands a baby placed on their partner's attention, or feeling excluded when breast/chestfeeding babies preferred being held by the lactating parent, both of which are experiences commonly reported by new fathers.

'She needs me, he needs her. So I do what I can to support her'

(Pallas)

Exclusion, marginalisation and fear

LGBTQ+ new and expectant parents face exclusion and marginalisation from policies, services and communities. Even where a service or community is inclusive, parents may be concerned before accessing the service that they might be excluded or marginalised, based on their own previous experiences, or experiences of other LGBTQ+ people. Every participant said that they had been or currently were worried about being excluded from services aimed at new or expectant parents. This concern limited the services that some accessed. Most participants had gone on to experience inclusion from most services, but also marginalisation from their experience of using some services, or outright exclusion from some services. Not being able to predict which services would be inclusive and which would not created stress for new parents.

Language that excludes

For the majority of the participants, being excluded began with the forms used to register for perinatal services, often called a booking-in form. Most parents found that the form was designed to only capture the details of the biological parents.

'The first problem we faced was that on the NHS form there was no way to put Margot's details down as anything else but the father'

(Lilja)

In some cases, an attempt at inclusion had been made, and 'father' had been replaced with 'partner'. This sometimes led to inappropriate medical questions being asked of non-gestational mothers. In other cases it did not allow for details to be accurately recorded if the non-gestational mother was a biological parent, either because her egg had been used, or because she was a trans woman. All of these experiences marginalised participants.

'We should be able to exist on paper, in our medical records'

(Margot)

One participant had a very different experience, and found that the booking-in forms used by their NHS Trust reflected their family situation well.

'From first form they had donor conceived. They had all the options that fit our family when you looked at parentage. They had family histories, they took Aisha's as well and they had a box for adopted'

(Fatima)

'We should be able to exist on paper, in our medical records'

(Margot)

One healthcare professional described how this problem had been addressed within their NHS Trust by creating multiple options for recording more than two parents' details, and linking different questions to each option selected. This allowed for the appropriate medical details to be captured about the gestational parent and the genetic parents or donors, alongside social details about the parents who would be raising the baby. They were keen to stress that adding these additional options did not disadvantage heterosexual couples who had conceived at home, who would simply choose to enter the details for the mother and father. Rather, adding more options for recording LGBTQ+ families' details had improved the experience for heterosexual couples who had had assisted conceptions, as they could now record information for gamete donors and alongside the mother and father's information.

The language used on forms, to describe relationships and to describe services can include, marginalise or exclude LGBTQ+ parents, and participants' expressed strong views about this. It was important to everyone interviewed that non-gestational mothers were not referred to as the mother's partner, but that their parenting role was acknowledged – a view which has been echoed in work with fathers^{35,36}. Phrases which replaced father but differentiated between the gestational and non-gestational parent – such as 'co-mother' and 'non-biological mother' or 'other mum' – were universally disliked and viewed as marginalising. It is important to emphasise here that participants used a variety of terms for themselves and used different terms in different contexts. Which language choices feel most inclusive is changeable, and there is not an agreed terminology that can simply replace 'mother and father' for LGBTQ+ families. Employing LGBTQ+ inclusive language therefore requires those working with perinatal populations to ask about individual parents' preferences, then record and use that language when talking to those parents.

'All parents are welcome. Do you mean the dad or the mum can come? Or is it any parents, any gender identities are welcome to come?'

(Margot)

Individual choices in language cannot be utilised when advertising services. When signalling that a service was LGBTQ+ inclusive, most participants preferred that a universal term such as 'parent' was used instead of replacing 'mother' or 'father' with another term. However they qualified that when generic terms such as 'parent' were used, LGBTQ+ inclusion should be made explicit alongside this.

Inclusion, marginalisation and exclusion in group settings

Establishing a social network supports new parents, meaning antenatal and parent and baby groups are common and useful. Attending a group for new or expectant parents as an LGBTQ+ woman comes with the potential for marginalisation, discrimination or exclusion. Most participants had attended some group setting, although several said they had chosen not to attend any because of concerns about inclusivity, and about half the participants had limited the groups they attended because of potential discrimination, marginalisation or exclusion.

Participants who had attended antenatal groups reported mixed experiences. In many antenatal classes, those attending are divided into mums and dads subgroups for some

discussions. This posed a problem for a number of participants, who felt that they did not belong in the group with other women as they were not pregnant, but did not belong in the group with men, because they were not fathers.

'I just feel out of place in both'

(Pallas)

Those who had experienced attending antenatal groups that divided along gendered lines had mostly been put into the group with fathers, although one participant reported being given the choice of which group to join. Those who had been placed in the group with fathers described everyone being very polite to them, but had not had particularly good experiences.

'Kate would find herself sat in a group of cis men and they'd be like, you know how it works, so you tell us how it works'

(Hannah)

Some participants had chosen to attend private antenatal education groups instead. Several described strategies they had used to check whether the group would be inclusive of them. These strategies included reading websites very thoroughly to see whether LGBTQ+ parents were explicitly mentioned, looking at the training an antenatal teacher had listed to check whether it included training in LGBTQ+ parents' needs from a training provider the participant felt was appropriate, and contacting the class provider directly to ask how they would include LGBTQ+ parents.

'We picked a private prenatal class that had specifically testimonials from lesbian couples. And she said outright I support same-sex partners, all birth partners, of any gender identity are welcome'

(Lilja)

Others wanted to attend antenatal classes, but found that they could not find a group where they felt certain they would be welcomed. Several participants reported regretting that they hadn't found a group to attend, because they felt it would have increased their local social support network.

'We inquired about NCT, we asked a few places, what's your diversity like? And she said, 'Oh, we don't know cause we don't check''

(Helen)

A different kind of exclusion happened for some families where one parent was a trans woman. Some participants in these families felt that they were read as a heterosexual couple, and so had to fight even harder to have their queerness recognised, especially within NHS settings. One participant felt less effort was made to remember their pronouns, or their partner's, or that they had multiple partners, because they were viewed as a heterosexual family:

'I think our journey would've been very different if we'd been treated like a queer family. But because we looked like a nuclear family, that reduced our options'

(Isabelle)

Once their baby had been born, some participants attended parent and baby groups, although others chose not to do so because they were concerned about potential exclusion. The language used to describe the group was felt to be important by the majority of the participants in working out whether they would be welcomed, often leaving them unsure about attending 'mum and baby' groups.

'If they're labelled as 'mummy and baby', can you show up with two mums? Could we both show up? Or is the assumption that it's one adult, one baby?'

(Lilja)

Non-gestational mothers in particular were concerned about attending groups that were labelled in this way, as they were uncertain about whether only mothers who had given birth would be expected or welcomed.

'At some I've felt, as a non-mum mum, I don't fit in here'

(Buffy)

When non-gestational mothers did attend such groups, they sometimes found the assumption that they had given birth to be difficult to respond to without revealing a high level of personal information to someone they had recently met. Some expressed that they were tired by repeatedly explaining their family. Being met with an assumption that they had given birth also led to internalised invalidation of their parental role.

'It made me feel a little bit like I was like trying to claim something that I'm not entitled to'

(Florence)

The majority of the participants had found at least one group where they felt welcomed and included. Even in groups that they described as enjoying and feeling safe in, some participants experienced negativity towards them because they were LGBTQ+ parents. Many were almost dismissive of these experiences, saying they were something they routinely expected to receive.

'It never got that bad that I couldn't handle it. It was just like, not usually words, it's more looks'

(Marcia)

However, these experiences did then impact whether participants said they would choose to risk accessing other unknown services in the future.

A few participants experienced more direct challenges from other parents, which they found distressing, such as the comments Ruby experienced from another pregnant woman and her friend in the waiting room of an antenatal clinic:

'They were like, what the hell? I mean, how did she even get pregnant? They actually asked us how I got pregnant. It was hard'

(Ruby)

Such encounters may affect whether parents feel safe in attending similar appointments, or groups in the same venue in future.

Participants were unanimous in describing what they needed from a group leader if they experienced discrimination or exclusion from other parents within the group. The group leader needed to be clear that LGBTQ+ parents were welcome, and that neither homophobia or transphobia would be tolerated. Group leaders needed to have a good understanding of the ways in which discrimination might take place, including invasive questioning of LGBTQ+ parents about the conception of their child, the use of language that questioned parenting relationships, such as 'real mum', and deliberate misgendering or refusal to use someone's pronouns.

LGBTQ+ parents who face multiple oppressions may find they are excluded from groups more often than those who face fewer forms of societal oppression. Black participants, disabled participants and transgender participants all described more experiences of being excluded than white, non-disabled cisgender LGBTQ+ women. In some cases, they also experienced exclusion from LGBTQ+ parents' groups.

'We're an anomaly. We're mixed race and also same sex'

(Pallas)

Fears of future exclusion

Participants were not only concerned about being excluded themselves, but were concerned about whether their child would experience exclusion as they got older. Several participants described interviewing childminders and nurseries to check how inclusive they were. They wanted to know whether the settings encouraged children to play 'mums and dads' in diverse ways, such as 'mums and mums' and 'dads and dads', whether they had storybooks that included different family forms, how they handled Mothers' Day and Fathers' Day, and whether there were any other children of LGBTQ+ families in the setting. Some found that nurseries were able to answer these queries easily, and had a good understanding of how to include children from LGBTQ+ families, whilst others found that the settings did not really understand their concerns. Most parents expressed greater concerns about the exclusion their child might

face when entering school, as they felt they had less chance to influence whether a school was inclusive.

'I think it's easy when he's a baby, but I think the problems are going to be when he's in school. I'm worried about that'

(Marcia)

Alongside this, parents were aware that they might need to fight for their children to be fully included, as children of LGBTQ+ families at any point in their childhoods. Participants talked about the potential need to advocate for their child's inclusion across a wide range of situations, including with their own families, educational settings and with their child's friends' parents. This had been a consideration for the majority from before conception, but their own experiences of exclusion during the perinatal period had often solidified this knowledge.

'You are signing up to be an advocate for another small person in a world that is not quite ready. You need to be ready to be uncomfortable if you need to be, to stand up for them'

(Fatima)

Registering the birth

In the UK there are complex rules dictating when two women can be listed on the birth certificate. They can both be listed if:

- They are married or civilly partnered and conceive through a fertility clinic
- They are married or civilly partnered and conceive at home with a donor via artificial insemination
- They are not married or civilly partners, but conceive through a fertility clinic and complete the appropriate paperwork prior to conception

All participants had conceived in one of these ways and had done so deliberately because they were aware of the law and wanted to ensure they would both be granted Parental Responsibility. Despite this, almost all of the participants experienced difficulties in registering their baby's birth.

'They didn't know what to do. There was a head office in London they had to call to ask how to do it. And it took ages'

(Cleo)

Several were interviewed for significant periods of time about how they had conceived and were asked to produce marriage or civil partnership certificated and paperwork from the fertility clinic repeatedly within the interview, sometimes by multiple people. Participants expressed frustration that, having invested so much time into deciding how to have a baby,

as well as time and money into conceiving, obtaining the document officially recognising them as parents was unnecessarily challenging.

'This should be a nice experience. I'm feeling like I'm being interrogated here. Like 'how did you get this baby?''

(Cleo)

Other participants faced less difficulty in actually registering the birth, but found that the information had been entered incorrectly due to heterosexism. One participant who had two children found that incorrect information was entered or requested at both registrations.

With the second baby, the Registrar had recorded the non-gestational parent's name, but then asked for the husband's occupation, and had been confused that there was no husband.

A further difficulty was encountered when trying to register the birth of a baby for trans women and their partners. Trans mothers who had Gender Recognition Certificates and who were also married or civilly partnered to the gestational mother were able to register as 'parent' in the same way as cis non-gestational mothers. Trans mothers who either did not have a Gender Recognition Certificate or who were not married or civilly partnered to the gestational mother could only be registered as fathers. In addition, they had to register using male titles such as Mr.

'The lady got extremely confused because Kate had been the one who changed her name when we got married, but she was the non-gestational parent. She'd assumed the gestational parent changes their name as hetero couples do, and had put Kate as the gestational parent. We had to do the whole thing again'

(Hannah)

'In the father bit there was no appropriate title, but he wouldn't let me complete the form without putting in a title. A father is only allowed to be Mr or Dr or things like that'

(Isabelle)

Work and Employment

Several participants who conceived through clinics described facing difficulties in taking leave from work for appointments at fertility clinics. As the timing of appointments depend on the ovulatory cycle, it is usual for daily appointments to be needed for an unknown period of time.

This means advance notice cannot be given to an employer, as the person receiving treatment will only be told at the end of each appointment whether they need an appointment the following day, and what time that will be^{37,38}. Whilst this is also a difficulty faced by heterosexual couples using assisted conception services, social infertility means it is an employment-related challenge faced by a higher proportion of LGBTQ+ people who are trying to conceive. Following the birth, the terminology of 'paternity leave' was experienced as marginalising by all of the non-gestational mothers interviewed.

Several participants had experienced discrimination at work because they were LGBTQ+ non-gestational parents. Whilst other mothers in similar roles were permitted to work flexibly to facilitate childcare, both Cleo and Buffy were told that they were not permitted to do so, because they had not given birth. In Cleo's workplace, other men who had children and other women who returned from maternity leave were permitted to work flexibly, and in Buffy's case their manager agreed to flexible working, then rescinded this without explanation. This led to both Cleo and Buffy leaving their employment, which she felt was due to her being a non-gestational mother.

'it is definitely a mix of sexism and homophobia'

(Cleo)

This mixture of homophobia, sexism and 'the motherhood penalty' combines to make non-gestational LGBTQ+ women who are parents especially vulnerable in employment.

Since 2015, non-gestational parents in the UK have been able to take Shared Parental Leave in addition to Paternity Leave. Shared Parental Leave allows fathers and non-gestational mothers to take up to 50 weeks leave from work (of which 37 weeks are paid) in the first year of their baby's life. Uptake of Shared Parental Leave is very low, with only around 2% of eligible families utilising it. Over half the participants in this study said the non-gestational parent in their family took Shared Parental Leave.

'I took shared parental leave. And apparently nobody ever takes that at all. And I've taken a career break for after the maternity leave'

(Margot)

All participants who took Shared Parental Leave said they were the first people in their organisation to have taken it.

'I was basically the only person trying to access Shared Parental Leave, which was weird. I think it was probably one of the first times that they'd done it in the company'

(Hannah)

Being the first people in an organisation to take Shared Parental Leave meant participants were faced with some additional challenges. One participant found that the wording in their organisation's policies only referred to mother and father throughout. Another was incorrectly told, after handing in their notice, that they would be required to repay the Shared Parental

Leave pay because they had left their employment within a set time, when in fact this was a requirement under the Maternity Leave and Adoption Leave policies, but not the Shared Parental Leave policy. Despite involving Human Resources and their Trade Union, the matter took several weeks to resolve causing significant stress because the participant felt financially forced to rescind the notice and continue to work in a role they wished to leave.

A number of non-gestational parents had taken further time off, or reduced their hours at work, to enable them to spend equal amounts of time with their babies as the gestational parent. Some were the primary carer for their baby.

'We both work four days a week, and then we have one day a week caring for Xenia each'

(Meira)

Information and service gaps

Perinatal services were designed with cisgender heterosexual monogamous couples in mind. Whilst there is significant work underway to make services accessible to everyone who becomes a parent who does not fit into this group, there are still areas where there is absolutely no provision for LGBTQ+ women. These gaps exist in both the services and information available. Three gaps were discussed by participants: postnatal sexual health advice; breast and chestfeeding information and support for non-gestational parents; and perinatal mental health services for non-gestational mothers.

NHS policy states that women who have given birth should be offered information both about sexual health and contraception before they leave hospital, or before midwives leave a homebirth. Participants reported that these conversations only included information about contraception, which they did not require.

The doctor said 'We need to talk about contraception. What sort of contraception are you going to be using after you've given birth? And Kate said 'Yeah, no, she's good, but she's not that good'. He went 'Oh my goodness'. And he just left

(Hannah)

All participants who recalled being given such advice said that the advice was unsuitable for them, and some felt it was delivered insensitively. These conversations were often repeated with GPs at postnatal checks, and with health visitors. Several participants discussed finding these conversations frustrating, as they felt their relationships were invalidated. For those who had invested significant time and money into having their baby, the conversations were distressing.

'My partner was in the room and was obviously the other parent. The nurse handed me a flyer and said 'You're so fertile in the next 10 weeks, you need to be really careful that you're not pregnant again'. I'm like, what's wrong with you?'

(Helen)

Whilst none of the participants in this research required contraceptive advice, it is important to remember that some LGBTQ+ people will benefit from such advice, and that an individualised approach should be taken.

Several participants said that they would have liked information about resuming sexual relationships, but none felt confident that healthcare professionals would be able to give appropriate advice for anyone who was not heterosexual.

Most LGBTQ+ women who are non-gestational parents will have the potential to breast or chestfeed their babies^{39,40}. How easy it is for a non-gestational parent to lactate depends on a similar range of factors to gestational parents, alongside some additional factors such as whether they have been pregnant, given birth, breast or chestfed themselves, and if so how long ago this was³⁹. Unless they are still lactating, lactation will need to be induced. This usually involves a schedule of using a breastpump every few hours for some weeks or months before starting to feed their baby, and may involve taking medication as well⁴¹.

Breast or chestfeeding their baby is something that is very important to some non-gestational mothers, and something that other non-gestational mothers will not wish to try⁴². If the non-gestational parent faces fertility challenges or is unlikely to become pregnant themselves, breast or chestfeeding may carry more significance^{40,42}.

'I looked into inducing lactation, but I would need drugs, and the NHS doesn't do it at all'

(Margot)

Around half of the research participants said that the non-gestational parent had considered breastfeeding, and several had breastfed their babies for periods of time ranging from a few months to around a year. In this research, gestational mothers had also breastfed the babies who were breastfed by non-gestational mothers, although this is not always the case within LGBTQ+ families⁴³. No non-gestational mother in this research had received support via the NHS on their breast/chestfeeding journey. Even finding information about inducing lactation was very difficult for participants, as very little research has been carried out. The biggest gap encountered by non-gestational parents who wanted to breast or chestfeed was that they were not anyone's patient. They were outside of the midwifery scope of practice and were not an obstetric patient. GPs rarely had the expertise to support someone to achieve their induced breast/chestfeeding goals.

Whilst some midwives are knowledgeable about non-gestational mothers lactating, most are not, and in other research, some LGBTQ+ non-gestational mothers have been told by healthcare professionals that they are considered a milk donor, rather than a breastfeeding mother⁴³. Conversely, one non-gestational mother in this research was delighted to find that she was treated as a breastfeeding mother during the immediate postnatal period.

'Because I was feeding, they said that I didn't have to stick to the visiting time'

(Buffy)

Buffy's experience outside of this was less positive. They were particularly frustrated that after having spent nearly £40,000 conceiving their baby because of inequalities for same-sex couples within NHS funding, they then had to pay for a private lactation consultant, due to a lack of knowledge amongst NHS healthcare professionals about inducing lactation in same-sex couples,

'I sat in this office of this midwife and just broke my heart because she essentially told us that we were neglecting the child because of how we were feeding her'

(Buffy)

then had to pay for an appointment with a private GP to be prescribed medication to support this, and then had to pay for the private prescription to be fulfilled due to a lack of support for co-breastfeeding amongst same-sex couples. The lack of knowledge amongst NHS healthcare professionals later endangered their baby, as incorrect information about how often each mother should feed the baby and for how long resulted in their baby becoming malnourished and losing significant amounts of weight, despite two separate healthcare professionals reassuring them that they were feeding appropriately. When a more knowledgeable healthcare professional told them that they were not feeding appropriately, this information was communicated poorly:

Another gap in both information and service provision is mental health support for non-gestational mothers. Mental health services for fathers are acknowledged as being sparse in comparison to the services available for mothers⁴⁴, but there are no NHS services at all that are targeted at non-gestational mothers.

'There were a lot of services around to help me, but not really much to support Cleo.'

(Marcia)

Several non-gestational mothers had experienced challenges to their mental health during early parenthood. For some, becoming a parent exacerbated existing mental health difficulties:

'My anxiety got worse about going outside with him'

(Margot)

Others experienced new challenges to their mental health, sometimes as a result of witnessing their partner's traumatic birth. For LGBTQ+ parents who have the physical ability to become pregnant, witnessing their partner's traumatic birth may have impacts that are different to the impact this would have on a cisgender father. One potential impact is the development of a strong fear of giving birth, called secondary tokophobia. Several

participants in this research said that witnessing their partner's traumatic birth had made them change their mind about either becoming pregnant themselves, or about how they'd like to give birth.

'We've agreed that she'll have an elective caesarean. She doesn't want to give birth vaginally, because she's seen me go through things'

(Meira)

Accessing appropriate support for secondary tokophobia for someone who has not given birth presents challenges. Maternal perinatal mental health services are usually only accessible to women who have given birth. In 2019, the UK Government announced the launch of new paternal mental services, although the rollout of these services has been disrupted by the pandemic. It is unclear whether these services are universally available to non-gestational mothers.

'Before she was pregnant, I always thought I wanted to be pregnant and have a baby. The birth, for me it was horrendous. I have no idea how I'd approach birth now'

(Florence)

Non-gestational mothers might also choose not to access services that they perceive are 'for fathers'. Several participants in this research said that they would not wish to access paternal mental health services, and as a result felt there was no support available for their mental health.

'I'm not a dad. And there's a particular experience that birth mothers go through, which won't cater to me'

(Pallas)

As a result some non-gestational mothers who participated in the research were left without any appropriate services to support their mental health postnatally, despite identifying that they needed them. In some cases negative interactions with healthcare professionals during the perinatal period were also a barrier to seeking help.

'I'm kind of frightened of saying anything because if I feel like I'm struggling, is somebody going to and take baby away? I don't think it's helped because of what she [previous health visitor] said'

(Buffy)

A topic discussed by three participants were the complicated feelings they had about donor conception. Here, there was a complete absence of information about or services to help LGBTQ+ parents process their complex mixture of gratitude to the donor for making their family possible, love for the child they had, and:

'Grief, it's an ongoing process, the... loss of the child that you really want, who's half you and half your partner'

(Meira)

Whilst sessions with in-house counsellors are mandatory for those attempting donor conception via a fertility clinic⁴⁵, these sessions were designed for cisgender heterosexual couples, and therefore focus mostly on the topic of disclosing donor conception to any future child – something which is less relevant to the majority of LGBTQ+ women⁴⁶. The sessions also end before conception, and there are no NHS leaflets, advice or services aimed at supporting LGBTQ+ parents with these ongoing complex feelings.

Policy, education and campaigning briefs

It is evident from the research findings that there are significant areas of inequality faced by LGBTQ+ women who become parents. In some of these areas, improvements to policies, services, or the education of professionals who work with new and expectant parents could result in radical change for LGBTQ+ parents. Drawn from the research findings, a series of four briefings have been produced. Each sets out one inequality faced by LGBTQ+ parents, alongside suggested action points.

Accurate fertility information

Current situation

Information about both the statistics for conceiving through assisted conception are homogenised figures based on any form of assisted conception. NHS advice for pregnancy and birth choices homogenises any form of 'assisted conception' as a single risk factor.

The problem

1. LGBTQ+ women who face social rather than medical infertility are not able to get accurate information about the likelihood of conceiving via IUI compared to IVF. IVF is more costly than IUI, and comes with health risks to the gestational parent and to the pregnancy, but may be chosen by LGBTQ+ women based on the inaccurate statistical information they are given
2. LGBTQ+ women who have conceived via IUI or home insemination may be inappropriately categorised as having high risk pregnancies, and receive inappropriate information about the risks and benefits of interventions such as induction of labour

Changes needed

- HFEA to require fertility services to report disaggregated conception rates, with markers for social infertility only, versus likely medical infertility, and this information to be given to patients who face social infertility
- Fertility clinics to include information about the health risks of IVF compared to IUI more prominently in the information given to patients
- NICE guidance on perinatal care following assisted conception to define forms of assisted conception, and provide appropriate guidance for different kinds of assisted conception

Birth registration

Current situation

Two women, including trans women who have a Gender Recognition Certificate, can be registered on the birth certificate if they are married or civilly partnered and have conceived through any form of artificial insemination (including home artificial insemination). They may also be able to both be registered on the birth certificate if they are not married or civilly partnered, but have conceived in a fertility clinic and have completed the correct paperwork. Trans women who do not have a Gender Recognition Certificate but are the biological parent to their child can be registered as the father, but must choose a male title.

The problem

1. Registrars are not consistently confident in how to register the birth of a baby who has two mothers. This may result in LGBTQ+ women being treated poorly during the registration of their baby, or to inaccurate registrations
2. Many trans women will not wish to be registered as the father of their child, or to have to choose a male title if they do so. The process to acquire a Gender Recognition Certificate is lengthy, presenting a barrier to more appropriate registration
3. It is discriminatory that trans women who are married to the gestational mother can be registered as a parent, but trans women who are not married must register as the father of their child if they wish to have Parental Responsibility

Changes needed

- Further guidance and training is needed for Registrars to ensure they are consistently confident in registering the birth of a baby with two mothers
- Changes are needed to either the requirement of titles for parents registering a birth, or to the titles available to them
- Consideration is needed to the legal definition of father versus parent on birth certificates. This may link to campaigns for more appropriate recognition of trans men who are gestational parents
- The production of guidance for LGBTQ+ women on registering the birth of their baby may be useful

Co-lactation support

Current situation

Non-gestational parents who wish to chest or breastfeed their babies are outside of the scope of midwifery practice and are not obstetric patients. GPs, midwives and lactation consultants may be approached by non-gestational parents for support in inducing lactation.

The problem

1. There are no national standards about the appropriate care for inducing lactation in a non-gestational parent
2. There is little research globally about the optimal induction of lactation protocol
3. Few healthcare professionals have any training in or knowledge of induced lactation
4. Non-gestational parents may access private lactation support, or may rely on internet advice of varying quality to induce lactation
5. A lack of knowledge about and appropriate support for the induction of lactation can pose a threat to a parent's or baby's health

Changes needed

- Research into appropriate regimes for inducing lactation is needed
- National guidelines based on this research should be produced
- Consideration should be given to extending the scope of practice of a healthcare profession to include lactating parents who have not given birth. Appropriate training should accompany this
- Urgent interim guidance should be created until fully evidence-based guidelines are available, accompanied by training for sufficient designated healthcare professionals to ensure the wellbeing of newborns who are chest or breastfed by non-gestational parents
- Urgent NHS interim guidance for non-gestational parents who inducing lactation or chest or breastfeeding should be created

Non-gestational mums' support

Current situation

LGBTQ+ non-gestational mothers may face challenges to their perinatal wellbeing. They may need informal social support from their peers, or to access perinatal mental health services for further support.

The problem

1. Groups for new parents may not be inclusive of non-gestational mothers. Being inclusive includes having the appropriate language to describe parents, and also appropriate processes for dealing with heterosexism, homophobia and transphobia if it arises. Even where groups are inclusive, if this is unclear, non-gestational mothers may not access them
2. Perinatal mental health services may not be appropriate for non-gestational mothers to access, leaving them without appropriate perinatal mental health support
3. Reliance on bio-centric medical terms such as primiparous may mean that full reproductive histories are not taken from mothers who have been both non-gestational and gestational parents, leading to missed psychological challenges

Changes needed

- It would be beneficial to non-gestational mothers to have more opportunities to connect with other non-gestational mothers through group settings or online forums
- Changes are needed to perinatal booking in forms, to allow complete family histories to be recorded. Good practice examples exist, and should be rolled out nationally
- Consultation with LGBTQ+ parents and perinatal mental health professionals is needed to determine how to provide mental health services to non-gestational mothers and to other LGBTQ+ parents who fall outside of the scope of perinatal mental health services badged as Maternal or Paternal

Appendix 1 – Glossary

Chosen family	Chosen family is a term traditionally used in LGBTQ+ culture to refer to lifelong relationships which are more significant than friendships, but which are not sexual or romantic. Such relationships may take the place of relationships with biological or adoptive families where LGBTQ+ people are disconnected from their families
Donor	In this report donor is used to mean a sperm donor, who provides sperm to people with social and/or medical infertility, but who will not be considered a parent to any resulting children
Gestational parent	A person who is or was pregnant, and is or will take on a parenting relationship to the baby
Heterosexism	Is the assumption that being heterosexual is the default. It can result in policies and practices which treat everyone as though they were heterosexual unless they specify that they are not
Homophobia	Fear of – or prejudice towards – lesbian and/or gay people
Infertility, medical infertility, social infertility	Infertility means someone is unable to conceive or carry a pregnancy. Medical infertility means they cannot conceive/carry because of a medical problem. Social infertility means they cannot conceive/carry a baby because they don't have access to the needed gametes (sperm and eggs)
IUI	Intra-uterine insemination involves sperm being inserted through the cervix into the uterus through a thin tube. It is usually carried out in a clinical setting, but can be carried out at home
IVF	In-vitro fertilisation involves the removal of eggs through a surgical procedure. The eggs are fertilised outside of the body, and a few days later replaced in the uterus. Those undergoing IVF will usually take a variety of medications over several months to halt their natural reproductive cycle, and then artificially stimulate the production and release of a larger number of eggs
LGBTQ+	Lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer and other sexual or gender minority people
Non-gestational parent	A non-gestational parent is any parent who was/is not pregnant with their child. Fathers and adoptive parents are also non-gestational parents, but this term is used within this report to refer to the woman or non-binary person who is the partner of the gestational parent
Perinatal	The perinatal period is the time from conception until one year after the birth of a baby
Polyamorous	People who have sexual or romantic relationships with more than one person at a time, with the knowledge and consent of all involved
Polycule	A polycule includes all partners (and their partners) of a polyamorous person
PTSD	Post-traumatic stress disorder is a mental health condition. It can result from a traumatic birth
Transphobia	Fear of – or prejudice towards – transgender people, including non-binary people

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